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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF IMMOBILIZING THE UZBEK NATIONAL CEREMONY AND TRADITIONAL SONGS IN YOUTH COMMUNITIES

ANNOTATION

This article talks about the development of Uzbek folk customs and ritual songs over time, which have become a valuable resource for educating generations as the totality of life. In addition, special mention is made in youth communities of the importance of the Uzbek national ceremony and the immobilization of traditional songs.

Key words: Ramadan, Olan, spirituality, traditional music, material cultural heritage, tradition, ritual, relatives, lapar, dervish.

ЁШЛАР ЖАМОАЛАРИДА ЎЗБЕК МИЛЛИЙ МАРОСИМИ ВА АНЪАНАВИЙ ҚЎШИҚЛАРНИ ИММОБИЛИЗАЦИЯ ҚИЛИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада авлодларни ҳаёт йиғиндиси сифатида тарбиялаш учун қимматли манбага айланган ўзбек халқ урф-одатлари ва маросим қўшиқларининг вақт ўтиши билан ривожланиши ҳақида сўз боради. Бундан ташқари, ёшлар жамоаларида ўзбек миллий маросими ва анъанавий қўшиқларни иммобилизация қилишнинг аҳамияти ҳақида алоҳида тўхталиб ўтилади.

Калит сўзлар: Рамазон, ўлан, маънавият, анъанавий мусиқа, моддий маданий мерос, урф-одат, маросим, қариндошлар, лапар, дарвиш.

В УЗБЕКСКОЙ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДЖАМОАТОРИИ РИТУАЛЫ И ТРАДИЦИИ ИММОБИЛИЗАЦИИ ИМЕЮТ ВАЖНОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассказывается о качественном воспитании и обучении узбекского народа ценному источнику узбекских обычаев и обрядов. Бундан подчеркнут важность отдельно проводимой узбекской национальной церемонии и традиции иммобилизации.

Калит суслар: Рамадан, Улан, духовность, традиционная музыка, материальное культурное наследие, обычаи, ритуалы, кариндошлар, лапар, дарвиш.

With the honor of independence, attention to our national-spiritual values, traditions, forgotten and historically valuable traditions, and the process of their reform became a priority.

Attention to our national values, traditions, and spiritual wealth has increased to the state level. Since the first years of independence, a lot of work has been done to preserve and restore the spiritual wealth left by our ancestors, including musical culture, and to keep pace with the times. . In this regard, our great spiritual wealth, which our ancestors left us as a legacy, serves as the main factor.

Traditions, rituals and holidays include hospitality traditions, customs related to morals, rituals related to child upbringing, cradle wedding, naming ceremony, circumcision wedding, it can include going to the marriage ceremony, greeting the bride, national and local parades, concerts, festivals, etc.

The ritual occurs when important events occur in a person's life and records and formalizes the most important events in people's lives (for example, birth, marriage, death). In Uzbek families, a system of rituals that serves as a kind of spiritual "staircase" for raising young families, recording important life events from the birth of a baby to growing up and building a new family ("The arrival of a baby in the world", "Giving a name", "Baby chill", "Cradle wedding", "Hair wedding", "Teeth wedding", "First step", "Circumcision wedding", "Muchal yosh", " "Nikah toy" etc.) came into existence [1, 2].

A cradle - wedding is a solemn ceremony held in honor of the birth of the first child in an Uzbek family. This tradition differs from one another in the regions of Uzbekistan with its own characteristics. There are various traditions related to the cradle. For example, the crib should never be lifted by two people from both sides, it should be lifted by only one person. The cradle is always kept in a clean place. Even when it is not in use, it is collected with its equipment and put in a clean place. All subsequent children born in the family will use this crib, which means that no new crib will be purchased for the next child born in the family.

In the circle of relatives of the baby, cradling is also called "cradle wedding" ceremony in the vernacular. This event is held in different order in different regions of Uzbekistan. Usually, the cradle is given to the eldest child by the girl's parents. The ceremony is held in the form of a family ceremony. The closest relatives of the bride and groom take part in it, and older grandmothers teach the young mother how to cradle the child.

Dervishona - Dervishona ceremony held by the people living in the steppes, engaged in animal husbandry, has a special place among the ceremonies held in the spring season. The day of this ceremony is determined by the elders of the local population, and men gather at a certain place around the village from early morning. Here, the work of beautification and cleaning carried out during the day is distributed. Mainly, cleaning and beautification works are carried out in cemeteries, water ditches, wells, ditches, roads and other objects commonly used by the population. Cattle (or sheep) bought with the money collected from the villagers are slaughtered and food is prepared in a certain place where the village gathers or in the open air. After the work is completed, all the residents who participated in this work gather again and agree on the work to be done during the year before the meal is served [3].

Summoning rain- is a ritual held in spring due to drought. It is mainly held by the people who farm in dry land (irrigated only by snow and rainwater). The ceremony is performed in different regions under the names "Soz xotin", "Sut xotin", "Suv xotin", "Sust xotin". The "Sust Xotin" ceremony was held with the participation of women in some villages of Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, and Namangan regions of Uzbekistan, and men in Shorchi, Koson districts and Uzbek lakais. At the appointed time, ten to fifteen women dressed a specially made doll in the clothes of an old woman. A woman carried him, and the others followed him, entering and exiting the houses of the village one by one. The owner of the house gladly gave them what he called. At the end of the ceremony, the symbolic doll was thrown into a nearby water basin by the villagers.

Nowruz (Persian - new day) is the first day of the new year according to the Shamsi (solar) calendar. It is an ancient traditional holiday of the peoples living in the countries of Central Asia and the East. The spring equinox (March 21 or 22) coincides with the entry of the Sun into Hamal. Nowruz is the holiday of starting agricultural work. On the holiday, mass public gatherings are organized, traditional dishes are cooked from fresh greens, and spring crops are planted.

Sumalak saili - is a public ceremony held in the first days of spring. The main dish consists of several customs associated with "sumalak". According to some information, the history of sumac is more than 3000 years old. Sumac is the only dish that can be cooked without adding salt. To prepare sumalak, you only need wheat water, flour, vegetable oil and water. It is considered to be the longest cooking dish, and it is dug for at least 22-24 hours so that it does not sink, and stones and nuts are thrown into it.

A lot of songs have been created in connection with the way of living and living life, traditions, rituals. Just as the rituals and customs are different in different regions, so are the songs dedicated to them. Songs about family holidays of the people. He decorated his ceremonies. people had fun, rested, and were inspired to new work activities during ceremonial holidays.

The first song in a person's life is a loving mother.

ALLA

Alla is a widespread traditional genre of lullabies. There is no nation or nation in the world that is not sung in their language. It is famous by the terms "bayki", "bayushki" in Russians, "huvdilar" in Turkmens, "lay-lay" in Azerbaijanis, "alli-balli" in Tatars. Alla's songs perform two tasks according to their socio-aesthetic value: the first is to lull children to sleep (the dictionary meaning of the word "Alla" is also to gently lull them to sleep). Such hypnosis or lulling is manifested in the process of singing. At the same time, the second function - educational-aesthetic essence is revealed. to introduce this child to life in tune. Alla's songs are important in raising children not only in Central Asia, but also among the peoples living in the countries of the Middle and Middle East [4, 5].

Allas are usually recited until the child reaches the age of three. Mother's love, wideness, and kindness are reflected in the pictures. In some allas, the expression of the environment that surrounds the child is exaggerated. In the allas of the Russian people, more attention is paid to familiarizing the child with the environment that surrounds him, and in the poetic praise of various birds and animals, they are also negative. , and try to show their creative features, but among the gods of the Uzbek people, there are no gods composed of poetic descriptions of animals, birds and insects, which are limited to the praise of a cradle or a swing. However, in Uzbek folk songs, there is a caressing tone related to the names of children of animals and birds: children are compared to lambs, mares, goblins, nightingales, and falcons. In fact, such a comparison has acquired naturalness at the heart of sincere relations with those animals.

The baby of the nightingale bird,
God, lamb, God.
A nest of trees
God, my child, God.
or: Nightingale is walking, alla-yo alla.
Kulluk is the voice of a bird, alla-yo alla.
My nightingale is my son, alla-yo alla.
Let it be my voice, alla-yo alla.

The most perfect example of allahilik is event-based allahs, such allahs are subject to a single plot and depict the moods created as a result of a scene of life events.

Features of the incident can be seen in humorous allas, as well as in gathering allas

*Slowly from the top
I'm fed up
Take scissors in my hand,
I'll give you a lamb
I cut a coat, alla.*

Parokanda allas are common among Uzbek mothers. Their important feature is that they are not built on the basis of a single plot. Each clause has an independent complete content. But such independence is only an external sign, because the logic of the content, the fact that it is still childish, arranges the clauses into a single thread, which is reinforced by the artistic-descriptive components such as weight, rhyme, radif and even refrain.

*I wake up in the morning,
I will stand up and follow you.
You are the day I lean on you.
Have mercy on me, my lamb.
Oh God.*

For a child, not the words of God, but the melody is pleasant. Because he doesn't understand words yet. And God's words are important for a mother, they are the cries of a mother's heart. Alla songs are a form of alla songs, which are mostly sung by men. That's why allahs are called male allahs. Allas are widespread among Uzbeks who are engaged in animal husbandry. Even when women are busy with household chores, it is the responsibility of men to caress and put the child to sleep. In such cases, fathers or grandfathers took the child on their knees and rocked them to sleep in a tone suitable for balance.

*God, my child, where are you?
Where is the camel that your grandfather gave you?
If you have a camel that your grandfather gave you,
Where are your children?*

Uzbek allas are a valuable source in the study of folk ethnography and ethnopedagogy. They depict a number of images related to children.

OH, RAMADAN

Several songs related to various traditions, ceremonies and rituals were created, including "Yo, Ramadan", "Barot Keldi", "Safar Kochdi", "Badik", "Buka-Bukavoy", "Sust Xotin", You can show things like "Pox". Among them, "Yo, Ramadan" was a song sung by children (and adults in the past) going from yard to yard during the month of Ramadan in the old calendar. On the surface, "Yo, Ramadan" looks like religious songs, but they are dominated by motives such as wishes for the owner of the house to have children, their generosity or stinginess. When the songs "Yo, Ramazan" are performed, the fluency of his analysis and the fact that he sings them with light humor are noticeable. Even today, it is common for children to go from house to house and perform songs expressing good wishes to the families they visited.

DIE

Olans, which are sung at weddings, sometimes on holidays, and at some gatherings, mostly without instruments, are more common among cattle breeders and farmers. In the fields, a shepherd boy and a shepherd girl argue about the pains of love, test each other in eloquence, eloquence, and humanity, and the competing parties give each other gifts. Olans are often composed of 11-syllable quatrains, usually with the first, fourth lines, sometimes four lines rhyming. For example, a young man says:

*While playing, while playing
I'll stop, see you
When I see you in the middle of the night?
You have fun, you laugh and twist your lips.*

In Olan, the joy, warmth of love, and joy of youth are sung very sincerely, mixed with the spirit of hope for the future. To be able to say the death in periods requires mastery of a specific potential, the art of performance. It is especially important to raise children with artistic and aesthetic taste, good manners, modesty, open volunteering, loyalty to friends.

BRIDE HELLO.

During the ceremony of introducing the bride to the close relatives of the groom, the bride's greeting or betochar songs are sung. According to tradition, the kayvani (waiter) says the bride from the gate to the house. The owners of the house and those who came to the wedding respond with "alík salam". Traditional greetings are read in Bukhara and Samarkand region. In "Kelin Salomda" (Kelin Salomda), he makes jokes to the bridegroom, adding jokes to his mother-in-law, uncles, aunts, and aunts.

The women who participated in "Kelin Salam" enjoy it and laugh. Critical humor and laughter are innocent, and no one will be offended by it. In fact, although the songs sung in "Kelin salom" have been composed before, it seems as if they were just created from the Kaivoni language, as if they fit the nature of the relatives of the new bride. In many places, "Kelin salom" consists of three lines, and in the Fergana valley, it consists of four lines. Basically, the first two lines rhyme with each other.

*Kayvani: The garden gave way from behind,
He gave money from his wallet
Greetings to his father-in-law.
Women: Hello Alik.
Kaivoni: The water has melted,
A son was born,
Greetings to his mother-in-law.
Women: Hello Alik.
Kaiwoni: Like a leech in a ditch,
His eyebrows and eyes are like elephants,
Like a beaten marrow
Greetings to Ovsini.
Women: Hello Alik.*

Kaivoni, a humorous bride, pours out greetings one by one, making people laugh. The given descriptions help to give a complete picture of the named person:

*Like a rock on the roof,
Like ivy in cotton,
As they walk,
Like a squirming kid,
Hello to the groom.
Greetings to his father-in-law like a blooming ivy.*

In some places, the names of people who are relatives of the bride, as well as those who served diligently at the wedding, are mentioned one by one:

*Like a stalled horse
Two pages are like a banot,
Greetings to Habibullah.*

Also among the people are the songs "Welcome" and "Toy mubarak", which are sung by the bridegroom in the direction of the bride, as well as by the girl when they come to the bride's house with the groom's attendants, and they are still widespread.

SUMMARY

It is known that examples of folk oral creativity, including folk epics, are the product of ancient creativity. The roots of the series of subjects, motifs and images in them go back to the mythological imaginations of our ancestors who lived in the oldest primitive times. It provides rich information about some motifs expressed in the epics and the customs and ceremonies of the peoples, the way of life, and the spiritual culture.

Uzbek folklore is the most important factor in building a democratic society based on the national ideals of the people, which is always consistent with the values and common interests of people. Therefore, at the time of the responsibility of creating the ideology of independence, the rich heritage of folk art is one of the spiritual tools to awaken the national spirit in the growing youth, to become children worthy of the nation and the homeland.

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